

Deposit Money Banks' Credit and the Real Sector Performance in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of bank credit on real sector development in Nigeria with time series data spanning from 1981 to 2020. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was used in the study to model this effect on the three components of real sector performance in Nigeria, such as the manufacturing, agricultural, and service sectors. Banks' credit, financial deepening, and the exchange rate are the independent variables used in the estimation. The study found that banks' credit has a negative effect on manufacturing in the short run but a positive effect in the long run; financial deepening has a mixed effect on the manufacturing sector; trade openness has a negative effect on the manufacturing sector; finance affects the agricultural sector positively in the short run but negatively in the long run; banks' credit has a positive effect on the service sector; and inflation affects service sector performance. The study also indicates that in Nigeria, bank financing has failed to account for the impact of real sector performance. The study recommends that commercial banks should grant more loans to the service and manufacturing sectors, and that they monitor the fund's use to ensure compliance.

Keywords: Banks' credit, real sector development, financial deepening, exchange rate

Introduction

Bank credit relevance in financing economic activity and development has been the subject of empirical research for decades. The modern economy is credit-driven, and as a result, credit is required by every sector of the economy for a variety of purposes. While credit played a vital role in the economic growth and development of emerging nations like Pakistan, Tahir et al. (2015) found that the allocation of credit to the various private sectors had a major impact on economic growth. More bank credit is thought to be beneficial to economic growth, according to Ibrahim et al. (2019). Lovemore (2017) opined that bank lending in Zimbabwe plays a critical role in boosting the manufacturing sector's performance by allowing companies to purchase the machinery they need to expand production.

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Bank credit helps to speed up the country's economic development by providing timely loans to businesses. It makes the large-scale production of commodities and other necessities of life easier, resulting in technological advancements and lower costs. The financial sector is made up of businesses and institutions that provide financial services to both commercial and retail consumers. Schumpeter (1911) addressed the link between financial and real sector growth. He believed that a well-structured financial system should support economic growth by encouraging profitable investments and effective bank resource allocation. According to the National Bureau of Statistics (2016), Nigeria's growth rate has slowed as a result of fewer industries enjoying strong expansion and a reduction in crude oil production. On this basis, there has been a renewed push to diversify the economy's productive base away from crude oil, and agricultural and manufacturing sub-sectors have been targeted in this direction.

In recent times, the manufacturing and agricultural sub-sectors in Nigeria have undoubtedly received some attention by being provided with cash through various banking agents other than deposit money banks. The impact of bank credits on the Nigerian economy's real sector will be the focus of this research. In this study, the real sector will be divided into three key sectors: manufacturing, agriculture, and service. Any economy's manufacturing sector is widely regarded as the engine of growth and a catalyst for long-term transformation and national development. This is due to its immense potential as a vehicle for generating income, creating jobs, contributing to the country's gross domestic product, and reducing poverty among the population.

The manufacturing sector dominates in terms of GDP contribution, and it has surpassed the services sector in several Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries (Anyanwu, 2010). Manufacturing enterprises' effectiveness is, however, dependent on the availability of resources such as raw materials and financial credit to meet consumer demand, which is why the financial sector was established to mop up credit from the surplus unit and transfer it to the deficit sector of the economy (Bada, 2017). Agriculture remains the economy's mainstay in Nigeria, as it employs the majority of the country's workforce, provides raw resources and food, and is one of the most effective weapons for ending extreme poverty, boosting shared prosperity, and feeding the 9.7 billion people expected to exist by 2050 (Obansa & Madeuekwe, 2012). When compared to other sectors, agriculture growth is two to four times more successful in raising incomes among the poorest. Agriculture is also critical to economic growth; it accounted for 4% of global GDP in 2018, and it can account for more than 25% of GDP in some emerging countries. Agriculture funding is one of Nigeria's most important economic policy instruments. The service sector is

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currently the world's fastest-growing industry. In most nations, it accounts for a large amount of gross domestic product and contributes significantly to total employment. As of 2015, the service sector contributed over 60% of Nigeria's GDP, with an average of about 33% of employment share compared to 7% for the industry. The performance of other sectors of the economy, such as manufacturing and agriculture, is known to be boosted by a productive service sector.

The service industry has the potential to significantly reduce income inequalities in the economy. Poor people can start service-sector businesses with little capital, resulting in economic empowerment and a reduction in income inequality. This reveals a critical missing link between the manufacturing and agriculture sectors, as bank credit supplied to the service sector improves the real sector's overall performance. The purpose of this study is therefore to analyse the influence of bank lending on the real sector, which includes the service sector as well as the manufacturing and agricultural sectors of the Nigerian economy. In addition, the study extends the period of study from 1980 to 2020 to cover the present state of the Nigerian economy.

Conceptual Clarifications

Deposit Money Bank Credit

Bank credit is the total amount of funds a person or business can borrow from a financial institution. Credit approval is determined by a borrower's credit rating, income, collateral, assets, and pre-existing debt. The principal role carried out by deposit money banks is to ensure there is an adequate flow of money to service deficit sectors of the economy and facilitate the movement of funds amongst economic units. The borrowing power supplied by the banking system in the form of loans to an individual, government, corporation, or organization is known as deposit money banks finance.

The Real Sector

The real sector denotes the real economic transactions of an economy. The real sector refers to the real economic transactions of a country, and the real economy relates to economic activities that generate goods and services, as opposed to a financial economy that is concerned exclusively with activities in the financial markets. The real sector economy in this context will be decomposed into three sub-sectors of the Nigerian economy: the manufacturing sector, the agricultural sector, and the service sector, respectively.

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Manufacturing Sector

The manufacturing sector is defined as a sub-set of the industrial sector in the secondary sector. The manufacturing sector involves the conversion of raw materials into finished goods, intermediate goods, or producer goods. Anyanwu (2012) defined the manufacturing sector as one that generates income, creates massive employment, provides inputs for the agricultural sector, and increases the foreign exchange earnings of the country through the foreign exchange gotten from the exportation of manufactured goods.

Agriculture Sector

The agricultural sector, according to Anyanwu (2012), is defined as the cultivation of land, raising and rearing of animals for the production of food for man, food for animals, and raw materials for industries. This includes cropping, livestock, forestry, fishery, processing, and marketing of these agricultural products. Agriculture is the major source of food for man, raw materials for industries, and a major player in the provision of employment opportunities, increase in income, reduction of poverty, and causes of environmental degradation.

The Service Sector

The service sector of the Nigerian economy is the third tier of the three sectors of the economy. The service sector is known as the tertiary sector or the service industry and is defined as the production of intangible goods and services that are important for the functioning of other sectors. In most cases, the service sector plays a complementary role in the development of the primary sector (agricultural) and the secondary sector (manufacturing). Price Water House Cooper (PWC, 2018) defined the service sector as the largest contributor to the Nigerian Gross Domestic Product, contributing an estimated 54.19% to GDP in 2010 and 56.9% to GDP in 2017 even in times of economic recession. That same report by Price Water House posited that the service sector is the highest employer of labour in Nigeria given its massive potential for income generation.

Deposit Bank Credit and the Agriculture Sector Relationship

Akhtar and Shan (1996) argue that bank credit can remove the financial constraints faced by farmers as it provides incentives to enable farmers to switch quickly to new technologies, which can enhance the achievement of rapid productivity and growth. Nwankwo (2012) states that in Less Developing Countries (LDCs) where agriculture is predominant, with credit facilities, the people can easily adjust to changing economic

conditions and meet seasonal and fluctuating income and expenditure. Since cash inflow and outflow typically occur at different times, he re-emphasised the continuous disbursement of loans to farmers to enable them to continue in agricultural production. Maftau (2003) argues that bank credit helps in reactivating, expanding, and modernising all types of agricultural enterprises that are considered economically feasible and desirable for the achievement of stated economic goals of self-sufficiency in agricultural production.

Deposit Banks Credit and the Manufacturing Sector Relationships

Oleka et al. (2014) asserted that deposit money bank credits and advances have a significant positive impact on the component of GDP of the manufacturing sector vis-à-vis economic growth. Ogar et al. (2014) argued that commercial banks' credits had a significant relationship with the manufacturing sector. Sogules and Nkoro (2016) also argued that banks' credits to the manufacturing sector exhibited a significant negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Ebi and Emmanuel's (2014) opined that increased bank credit to the industrial sector is significant in determining industrial sector growth in Nigeria. Ogege and Boloupremo (2014) opined that credit allocated to the production sector is having a significant positive effect on growth.

2.1.5 Deposit Bank Credits and the Service Sector Relationship

The high spread of lending rates has also constituted a serious disincentive to effective financial intermediation in Nigeria. Chete (2006) asserts that there is a unique long-run relationship between the interest rate and economic growth. He argued that the interest rate is an important determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. John and Terhemba (2016) also asserted that the inflation rate and interest rate harm manufacturing sector output. Imoughele and Ismaila (2013) opined that the bank rate of lending loans significantly affects manufacturing output in Nigeria. Oshikoya (1992) found a real interest rate to have a significant and negative impact on economic growth. Obamuyi (2009) asserts that real lending rates have a significant effect on economic growth.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on the financial intermediation theory and supported by the Wicksell theory of lending and loanable fund theory. The financial intermediation theory, according to Gurley and Shaw (1960), is based on the theories of informational asymmetry and agency theory. In principle, the existence of financial intermediaries is

explained by the existence of the following attributable factors: the high cost of a transaction, inadequate information at a useful time, and the method of regulation. The Wicksell theory of lending and economic growth, on the other hand, was postulated by a Swedish economist called Knut Wicksell in 1901, with strong influence from the quantity theory of money. Wicksell based his theory on a comparison of the marginal product of capital with the cost of borrowing money. He argued that if the interest rate of borrowing money was below the natural rate of return on capital, entrepreneurs would borrow at the money rate to purchase capital goods. This would lead to increased demand for all types of resources and, in turn, their prices, and vice versa. Finally, the loanable fund theory in economics is central to the theory of interest rates as it explains the determination of interest rates in terms of the demands for and supply of credit. According to Pearce (1992), loanable funds or credit is strictly the term used for funds that are available for lending in the money and capital markets and is usually considered within the context of the theory of interest rate.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Several empirical studies have been carried out on the relationship between deposit money banks' credit and the real sector's performance. Andabai and Eze (2018), in their study, examined a causality investigation on bank credit and manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria from 1990 through 2017. Using the vector error correction mechanism estimation as their method of analysis, they established that there was no significant relationship between bank credit and the manufacturing sector. They recommended that the interest rate be reduced to encourage the manufacturing sector towards achieving economic growth. Chinweoke et al. (2015) investigated the impact of commercial bank loans and advances to the agricultural and manufacturing sectors on the economic growth in Nigeria for the periods, 1994–2013 using the ordinary least square technique. The result of the study shows that banks' loans and advances to agricultural and manufacturing sectors have a statistically significant impact on economic growth. Nnamocha and Eke (2015) investigated the effect of bank credit on agricultural output in Nigeria via Error Correction Mode (ECM) using yearly data (1970–2013). Empirical results from the study showed that in the long run, bank credit and industrial output contributed a lot to agricultural output in Nigeria, while only industrial output influenced agricultural output in the short run. Ayunku & Eweke. (2020) investigated the impact of bank credit, macroeconomic dynamics, and the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Nigeria. Using the annual time series data from 1992 to 2016, the non-linear ARDL approach used for this study

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concluded that there exist negative impacts of both bank credits and macroeconomic variables proxied by government tax revenue, inflation rate, interest rate, and exchange rate on SME performance in Nigeria. The SME in the context of this study falls under the manufacturing sector. They recommended that loans channelled to boost productivity in SMEs should be monitored to avoid diversion for other unrelated purposes. Olusegun et al. (2014) reviewed the impact of commercial bank lending on Nigeria's aggregate economic growth using annual data for the period 1970–2011. It also reviewed the impact of bank credit on the growth of the services and 'Other sectors, as well as their sub-sectors of transport, communication, and public utilities; government and personal/professionals, respectively. The results showed that both previous and current year's credit to the 'Others' sector had a negative relationship with economic growth. In terms of the subsectors, the previous year's credit to public utilities and transport/telecommunications sub-sectors showed positive contributions to economic growth, while the impact of that of the current year was negative.

Research Design

This study adopts a quasi-experimental research design since it is the most suitable research design for the social sciences. The quasi-experimental research design enables the researcher to determine the cause-and-effect relationship between dependent and independent variables and does not rely on random assignment of data. Data for this study was sourced from the World Bank, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), and the Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin (2019). Finally, the essence of choosing the period 1981–2019 is to enable the researchers to evaluate the performance of agriculture in Nigeria before and after the world financial crisis of 2007–2008.

Model Specification

The study adopts the modified version of Daniel et al. (2019) model. Daniel et al. (2019) estimation of effect of deposit money banks real sector financing on economic growth in Nigeria. The linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables was expressed as thus:

$$RGDP = f(LDMBA + LDMBM + LDMBMQ + DMBLRRS)$$

$$RGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LDMBAt + \beta_2 LDMBMt + \beta_3 LDMBMQ_t + \beta_4 DMBLRRSt + \mu_t \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product (Dependent Variable)

β_0 = a constant;

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$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = Coefficients of the Independent Variables;

LDMBA = Loan of Deposit Money Banks to Agricultural Sector (Independent Variable);

LDMBM = Loan of Deposit Money Banks to Manufacturing Sector (Independent Variable);

LDMBMQ = Loan of Deposit Money Banks to Mining and Quarrying Sector (Independent Variable); DMBLRRS = Deposit Money Banks' Lending Rates to Real Sector (Independent Variable);

f = Functional Relationship;

t = Periods; and μ = Error term

The linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables in this study is expressed in three equations as thus:

Model one: The Manufacturing Sector Model

$MSO = f(BCMS, FD, INF, TOP)$

$$MSO_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BCMS_t + \beta_2 FD_t + \beta_3 INF_t + \beta_4 TOP_t + \mu_t \quad (3.2)$$

Where,

MSO_t = Manufacturing Sector Output at time t.

$BCMS_t$ = Bank Credit to Manufacturing Sector at time t.

FD = Financial deepening at time t

INF_t = Inflation Rate at time t.

Top = Trade Openness

$\alpha\beta$ = intercepts and unknown coefficients.

Model Two: The Agricultural Sector Model

$ASO = f(BCAS, FD, EXR)$

$$ASO_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BCAS_t + \beta_2 FD_t + \beta_3 EXR_t + \beta_4 TOP_t + \mu_t \quad (3.3)$$

Where;

ASO_t = Agricultural Sector Output at time t.

$BCAS_t$ = Bank Credit to Agricultural Sector at time t.

FD = Financial deepening at time t

EXR_t = Exchange Rate at time t.

EXR_t = Exchange Rate

$\alpha\beta$ = intercepts and unknown coefficients.

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Model Three: The Service Sector Model

$$SSO = f(BCSS, FD, EXR)$$

$$SSOt = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BCSS_t + \beta_2 FD_t + \beta_3 EXR_t + \mu_t \tag{3.4}$$

Where,

SSOt= Service Sector Output at time t.

BCSS_t= Bank Credit to Service Sector at time t.

TOP= Trade Openness

FD= Financial deepening at time t

EXR_t= Exchange Rate at time t.

$\alpha\beta$ = intercept and unknown coefficients.

Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 Results of Descriptive Statistics

	MSO	ASO	SSO	BCMS	BCAS	BCSS	FD	EXR	INF	TOP
Mean	2884.335	7300.857	11736.93	234.5260	3155944.	1047.556	16.36200	101.0401	9.587500	50.57838
Median	907.5699	1761.915	2447.369	30.03893	544997.2	348.4013	13.46500	106.4134	7.950000	50.74836
Maximum	12455.53	27371.30	46311.83	1179.691	12456251	3619.070	27.38000	381.0000	22.60000	81.81285
Minimum	26.88596	17.05218	64.24217	2.659800	24654.90	0.238600	9.060000	0.610000	1.900000	21.44693
Std. Dev.	3886.450	9012.435	16040.10	364.8682	3926360.	1217.280	5.868546	102.1023	5.877126	15.79082
Skewness	0.319793	0.013312	0.161620	0.579353	0.903100	0.707029	0.574038	0.960920	0.581481	-0.137121
Kurtosis	3.324734	2.644691	2.812907	3.981516	2.345650	1.986713	1.679486	3.244154	2.232561	3.227932
Jarque-Bera	11.78811	7.055743	9.054085	18.23466	6.150883	5.043854	5.103059	6.255132	3.235737	1.090858
Probability	0.002756	0.029367	0.010813	0.000110	0.046169	0.080305	0.077962	0.043824	0.198321	0.579593
Sum	115373.4	292034.3	469477.1	9381.040	1.26E+08	41902.24	654.4800	4041.603	383.5000	1972.557
Sum Sq.										
Dev.	5.89E+08	3.17E+09	1.00E+10	5192023.	6.01E+14	57789065	1343.153	406570.6	1347.084	9475.300
Observatio										
ns	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40

Source: Eview-10 Output.

From the above table, the mean and median values of manufacturing sector output are 2884.335 and 907.5699, respectively, while the mean and median values for agricultural sector are 7300.857 and 1761.915. Also, the mean and median values for the service sector are 11736.93 and 2447.369, respectively. The great dispersion of the mean

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from the median values of these sectors implies that these sectors do not have the resilience to withstand external aggression in the long run. The mean value for bank credit to the manufacturing sector is 234.5260, while the median value is 30.03893. This means that the median value dispersed greatly from the mean value, and it is evidence that bank credit cannot sustain stable growth in the Nigerian economy. The average of the series for bank credit to agricultural sector output is 3155944, while the median value is 544997.2. The fact that the median value is far from the mean value implies that agricultural sector output disperses greatly from the mean value and does not have the resilience to withstand external aggression in the long run. The average of the series for bank credit to service sector output is 1047.556, while the median value is 348.4013. The fact that the median value is far from the mean value implies that service sector output disperses greatly from the mean value and does not have the resilience to withstand external aggression in the long run.

Empirical Analysis

Model One: Manufacturing Sector Model

Table 2: Test for Unit Root

Variables	Level		First Difference		Order of Integration
	T. statistics	Critical Value	T. statistics	Critical Value	
LOG(MSO)	-1.048245	-2.938987	-4.983284	-2.941145	I(1)
LOG(BCMS)	-1.485368	-2.938987	-5.309524	-2.941145	I(1)
FD	-3.916103	-2.938987			I(1)
INF	-2.943793	-2.938987	-	-	I(0)
TOP	-2.341945	-2.938987	-7.257147	-2.941145	I(1)

Source: Authors Compilation

Table 2 depicts the stationarity test for the time series data used in the study. A close look at the data shows that all the series became stationary after first differencing, except the inflation rate. This means that the inflation rate was mean reverting or stationary at its level. Conclusively, there is a combination of series with different order of integration, and this serves as the justification for the adoption of autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models.

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Bound Cointegration Result for Model One

Table 3: Bounds Cointegration Result

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic : n=1000				
F-statistic	19.26917	10%	2.2	3.09
K	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		2.5%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37
Finite Sample: n=40				
Actual Sample Size	36	10%	2.427	3.395
		5%	2.893	4
		1%	3.967	5.455
Finite Sample: n=35				
		10%	2.46	3.46

A close look at the bounds cointegration result in Table 3 above indicates that there is a presence of a long run cointegration or long run relationship among the variables in the model. This is premised on the fact that the t-statistic value of 19.26917 is greater than the upper bound critical value of 3.49. Hence, the null hypothesis of no level relationship is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. To this end, the researcher proceeds to estimate the long run coefficient of the long-run relationship among the variable.

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Short Run Result/ARDL Error Correction Regression

Table 4: ARDL Error Correction Result

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Date: 05/30/22 Time: 06:39

Sample: 1981 2020

Included observations: 36

ECM Regression

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLOG(MSO(-1))	-0.533800	0.092263	-5.785621	0.0001
DLOG(MSO(-2))	-0.566784	0.107451	-5.274840	0.0002
DLOG(BCMS)	-0.024512	0.011742	-2.087559	0.0571
DLOG(BCMS(-1))	-0.021486	0.012411	-1.731199	0.1071
DLOG(BCMS(-2))	0.033936	0.012827	2.645707	0.0202
D(FD)	0.018192	0.004497	4.044994	0.0014
D(FD(-1))	-0.013069	0.003803	-3.436536	0.0044
D(FD(-2))	-0.005464	0.004049	-1.349602	0.2002
D(FD(-3))	-0.017596	0.004011	-4.386528	0.0007
D(INF)	0.003687	0.000664	5.549195	0.0001
D(INF(-1))	-0.003658	0.000901	-4.059796	0.0014
D(INF(-2))	-0.000203	0.000605	-0.334867	0.7431
D(INF(-3))	0.001014	0.000593	1.709423	0.1111
D(TOP)	0.000785	0.000979	0.802327	0.4368
D(TOP(-1))	-0.005993	0.001152	-5.202990	0.0002
D(TOP(-2))	-0.005304	0.001320	-4.019603	0.0015
D(TOP(-3))	-0.003445	0.001097	-3.141202	0.0078
CointEq(-1)*	-0.077928	0.006159	-12.65237	0.0000
R-squared	0.924630	Mean dependent var	0.170263	
Adjusted R-squared	0.853448	S.D. dependent var	0.110752	
S.E. of regression	0.042398	Akaike info criterion	-3.176565	
Sum squared resid	0.032357	Schwarz criterion	-2.384805	
Log likelihood	75.17816	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-2.900219	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.382218			

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

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Table 4 illustrates the ARDL error correction regression for the research on the effect of bank credit on the manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020. The R^2 -square is valued at 0.924630, while the R^2 -square adjusted is 0.8534468. This means that 85 percent of the total variation in the manufacturing sector is caused by the interplay of the variables in the model, while the remaining 15 percent is captured by variables in the error term. The Durbin Watson statistic valued at 2.382218 shows the absence of first-order autocorrelation in the residual. Finally, the error correction term appeared with the normal sign (-), and it is statistically significant at 5 percent. As a result, the past disequilibrium will be corrected at a rate of 7% per year. Hence, it will take 14 years and three months to attain full employment in the event of accepting the outcome of this research.

Evidence from the regression output shows that the one-year and the second-year lag values of the dependent variable, MSO(-1) and MSO(-2) lag values of the dependent variable NSO(-1) hurt the dependent variable and are statistically significant. This implies that an increase in the first and second-year lag values of the dependent variables (MSO (-1) and MSO (-2) will, all things being equal, amount to 0.53380 and 0.566784. By implication, manufacturing sector performance is a negative predictor of its present value in Nigeria.

In the short run, the coefficient of bank credit to the manufacturing sector (BCMS) is a negative predictor of manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. This implies that a unit increase in bank credit to the manufacturing sector will stimulate a further decrease in manufacturing sector performance at the rate of -0.024512 annually. The second-year lag value of bank credit to the manufacturing sector is a positive determinant of manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria, implying that credit to the manufacturing sector has an unstable temporal effect on the manufacturing sector's performance in the short run.

On the other hand, the coefficients of financial deepening (FD), inflation (INF), and trade openness (TOP) positively determine the manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. These effects, however, are also unstable, as their past values in the first and second years show that these variables negatively drive manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria.

Long Run Result

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Table 5 Trend Estimation

Levels Equation

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG(BCMS)	0.383681	0.229008	1.675400	0.1177
FD	0.232946	0.036088	6.454997	0.0000
INF	0.124402	0.044465	2.797734	0.0151
TOP	0.086064	0.026941	3.194552	0.0070
C	0.683148	0.771834	0.885097	0.3922

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.00

In the long run, the coefficients of financial deepening (FD), inflation (INF), and trade openness (TOP) positively affect manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria, resulting in a 0.232946, 0.1244, and 0.086064 unit increase in manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria, respectively. While the outputs of financial deepening and trade openness comply with a priori expectations, the output of inflation is contrary to economic theory. According to theory, an increase in inflation will lead to an increase in the cost of production, reducing the purchasing power of the naira, reducing the volume of raw materials, and causing a decline in output in the long run. The reasons for this anomaly could be that inflation may have raised the cost of borrowing or that the price increase may have increased the revenue of the manufacturers, which in the long run has stimulated further profit as they reinvest the profit they made previously.

Diagnostic Checking

Table 6: Post Estimating Test Summary

S/N	Residual Test	F.stat	Prob	OBS ^X R	Prob
1.	Normality Test	0.5496669	0.759698		
2.	Brench-Godfrey correlation test	serial 0.7555740	0.4928	4.346031	0.1134
3.	Heteroskedasticity test	0.862023	0.6332	21.35876	0.49877
4.	Cusum	Stable		Stable	

Sources; Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

Table 6 illustrates the post-estimation test for the empirical examination of the effect of bank credit on the manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020. The evidence presented above indicates that the residual followed a normal distribution because the probability value of the Jarque-Bera statistic of 0.549669 (0.759698) is greater than the 5% threshold. To corroborate the Durbin-Watson statistic, the serial correlation test conducted with the Breusch-Godfrey serial correlation test indicates the absence of serial correlation in the estimated equation. This assertion is premised on the fact that both the F-statistic value of 0.755140 and the observed R-square value of 4.346031 have chi-square or probability values of 0.4918 and 0.1138, which is more than the significant level of 0.05. On the other hand, the homoskedasticity assumption of classical linear regression is upheld. This implies that there is no evidence of heteroskedasticity in the residual of the estimated equation. The reason is that both the F-statistic value of 0.862023 and the Obsx R-square of 21.35876 have probability values of 0.6332 and 0.4987, which is greater than the threshold limit of 0.05. Finally, the model stability test, which is conducted with the cusum test, indicates that the estimated equation is stable within the specified limit.

Model Two: Agricultural Sector Model

Table 7: Unit Root Result for Model Two

Variables	Level		First Difference		Order of Integration
	T. statistics	Critical Value	T. statistics	Critical Value	
LOG(ASO)	-2.422117	-2.938987	-3.839979	-2.941145	I(1)
LOG(BCAS)	-1.096264	-2.938987	-5.578574	-2.941145	I(1)
FD	-3.916103	-2.938987			I(0)
EXR	2.465610	-2.938987	-3.825727	-2.941145	I(1)
TOP	-2.341945	-2.938987	-7.257147	-2.941145	I(1)

Sources; Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

Table 7 depicts the stationarity test for the study. A close look at the data shows that all the series became stationary after first differencing except financial deepening, which was mean reverting or stationary at level. Conclusively, there is a combination of

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series of series with different order of integration and serves as the justification for the adoption of autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models.

Cointegration Test

Table 8: Bounds Cointegration Test Result for Model Two

Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship

F-Bounds Test

Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	4.252086	10%	2.2	3.09
K	4	5%	2.56	3.49
		2.5%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37
			Finite Sample: n=40	
Actual Sample Size	36	10%	2.427	3.395
		5%	2.893	4
		1%	3.967	5.455
			Finite Sample: n=35	
		10%	2.46	3.46
		5%	2.947	4.088
		1%	4.093	5.532

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

A close look at the bounds cointegration result in Table 8 above indicates that there is the presence of a long run cointegration or long run relationship among the variables in the model. It could also mean that there will be a convergence in the long run. This is premised on the fact that the t-statistic value of 4.252086 is greater than the upper bound critical value of 3.49. Hence, the null hypothesis of no level relationship is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. To this end, the researcher proceeds to estimate the long run coefficient of the long run relationship among the variables.

Table 9: Short Run Result/ARDL Error Correction Regression Result

ECM Regression

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLOG(ASO(-1))	0.304970	0.106800	2.855531	0.0085
D(BCAS)	0.001046	0.000977	1.071100	0.2944
D(EXR)	0.002274	0.001253	1.814654	0.0816
D(EXR(-1))	0.002368	0.001325	1.786982	0.0861
D(FD)	0.007281	0.001443	5.045323	0.0000
CointEq(-1)*	-0.050984	0.009214	-5.533084	0.0000
R-squared	0.554288	Mean dependent var		0.188999
Adjusted R-squared	0.480003	S.D. dependent var		0.167939
S.E. of regression	0.121102	Akaike info criterion		-1.233355
Sum squared resid	0.439971	Schwarz criterion		-0.969435
Log likelihood	28.20039	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-1.141240
Durbin-Watson stat	1.607303			

* p-value incompatible with t-Bounds distribution.

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

The R^2 value is 0.554288, while the R^2 -square adjusted value is 0.480003. This means that the variation in the agricultural sector is a function of the interplay of the variables in the model, while the remaining 52 percent is determined by exogenous factors outside the ones in the model. The Durbin-Watson statistics valued at 1.607303 indicate the absence of first-order autocorrelation. The error correction term appeared with the normal sign (-), and it has statistical significance. This implies that the past

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disequilibrium will be corrected at a rate of 5% per year. Full equilibrium in this regard will take an average of 50 years.

In the short run, the past value of the dependent variable (ASV) is a positive determinant for the agricultural sector, and it is statistically significant at 5 percent. This means that the expansion of the agricultural sector can stimulate further positive values in the business world. The coefficient of financial deepening (FD) shows that an increase in financial deepening will result in a 7% increase in manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. This implies that financial deepening has a temporal influence on agricultural sector performance in Nigeria.

Table 10: Long-Run Result

Levels Equation

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG(BCAS)	0.004913	0.002296	2.140038	0.0423
FD	-0.007281	0.002077	-3.505602	0.0017
EXR	-0.049925	0.054888	-0.909592	0.3717
TOP	0.038570	0.055714	0.692278	0.4951
C	-13.66467	10.94428	-1.248568	0.2234

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

Table 10 illustrates the long-run estimate of the relationship between bank credit and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria throughout the study. Evidence inherent in the study shows that credit to the private sector (BCAS) is a positive determinant of agricultural sector performance. A unit increase in bank credit to the agricultural sector will, all things being equal, amount to a 0.004913 unit increase in agricultural sector performance in Nigeria. This implies that bank loans to the agricultural sector stimulate the growth of agricultural output in Nigeria. This assertion is consistent with economic theory and explains the cause of the present improvement in agricultural output in Nigeria, despite the increase in population and rising insecurities in the country. The coefficient of financial deepening (FD), on the other hand, is a negative determinant of agricultural sector performance. A unit increase in financial deepening will, all things being equal, amount to a 0.0007281 unit decrease in

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agricultural sector performance. By implication, financial deepening causes a decline in agricultural output, contrary to the apriori expectation. Reasons for this anomaly could be that there are too many middlemen between the real farmers in the country and the government; they divert the credit meant for the purchase of agricultural input to their private businesses or consumption instead of for the purposes for which it was approved in the first place. It could also mean that the fertility of the soil cannot sustain a further increase in agricultural output despite the increase in financial deepening due to poor techniques and technology used in farming. Specifically, to expand the farm output, the farmers must always incorporate or learn new ways of either planting or harvesting their produce without losing sight of what is required to improve its development.

Model Three: Service Sector Model

Table 11: Unit Root Result for Model three

Variables	Level		First Difference		Order of Integration
	T. statistics	Critical Value	T. statistics	Critical Value	
LOG(SSO)	-0.842998	-2.938987	-2.611310	-2.941145	I(1)
LOG(BCSS)	-1.250066	-2.938987	-7.799133	-2.941145	I(1)
FD	-3.916103	-2.938987	-	-	I(0)
INF	-2.943793	-2.938987	-	-	I(0)
TOP	-2.341945	-2.938987	-7.257147	-2.941145	I(1)

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

Table 11 depicts the stationarity test for the time series data used in the study. A close look at the data shows that all the series became stationary after first differencing, except inflation rate and financial deepening, which were mean reverting or stationary at level. Conclusively, there is a combination of series with different order of integration, and serves as the justification for the adoption of autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) models.

Cointegration Test

Table 12: Bound Co-integration Test for Model Three

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
F-statistic K	13.07873 4	10%	2.2	3.09
		5%	2.56	3.49
		2.5%	2.88	3.87
		1%	3.29	4.37
Actual Sample Size	36	Asymptotic: n=1000		
		10%	2.427	3.395
		5%	2.893	4
		1%	3.967	5.455
		Finite Sample: n=40		
		Finite Sample: n=35		
		10%	2.46	3.46
		5%	2.947	4.088
		1%	4.093	5.532

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

Table 12 illustrates the bound cointegration result in the investigation of the effect of bank credit on manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. A close look at the bounds cointegration result above indicates that there is the presence of a long-run cointegration or a long-run relationship among the variables in the model. It could also mean that there will be convergence in the long run. This is premised on the fact that the t-statistic value of 13.07873 is greater than the upper bound critical value of 3.49. Hence, the null hypothesis of a no-level relationship is rejected, while the alternative hypothesis

is accepted. To this end, the researcher proceeds to estimate the long-run coefficient of the long-run relationship among the variables.

Short Run Estimate for Model Three

Table 13: Short Run Result for Service Sector Output

ECM Regression

Case 2: Restricted Constant and No Trend

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLOG(SSO(-1))	-0.070057	0.114162	-0.613668	0.5476
DLOG(SSO(-2))	-0.334107	0.104316	-3.202842	0.0052
DLOG(BCSS)	0.001225	0.012858	0.095267	0.9252
DLOG(BCSS(-1))	0.033852	0.012628	2.680750	0.0158
DLOG(BCSS(-2))	-0.023978	0.013105	-1.829659	0.0849
D(FD)	0.003652	0.003199	1.141376	0.2695
D(FD(-1))	0.009263	0.003113	2.975644	0.0085
D(FD(-2))	0.005899	0.003055	1.931094	0.0703
D(INF)	0.000335	0.000467	0.717548	0.4828
D(TOP)	0.003193	0.000864	3.696865	0.0018
D(TOP(-1))	-0.007461	0.001060	-7.038722	0.0000
D(TOP(-2))	-0.006320	0.001080	-5.854230	0.0000
D(TOP(-3))	-0.006723	0.000988	-6.807133	0.0000
CointEq(-1)*	-0.047254	0.004689	10.07733	0.0000
R-squared	0.912487	Mean dependent var		0.177125
Adjusted R-squared	0.860775	S.D. dependent var		0.099253
S.E. of regression	0.037034	Akaike info criterion		-3.468651
Sum squared resid	0.030174	Schwarz criterion		-2.852838
Log likelihood	76.43573	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.253716
Durbin-Watson stat	2.621948			

Sources: Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

The table illustrates the short run and error correction output in the examination of the impact of bank credit on service sector performance in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020. The equation estimates show that the R²-square is 0.912489, while the R²-square adjusted is 0.860775. This means that 86% of changes in service sector performance can

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be attributed to the interplay of the model's variables, while the remaining 14% can be attributed to the error term. The error correction term appeared with the normal sign, and it is statistically significant at 5 percent. This means that the past disequilibrium will be adjusted at a rate of 4% per year. Thus, it will take about 25 years to attain full equilibrium when the outcome of this work is considered for policymaking.

In the short run, the coefficient of the past value of the dependent variable (SSO) (-2) has a negative impact on the service sector and is statistically significant at 5%. This means that the past realisation of the agricultural sector will, all things being equal, affect the present values negatively by 0.334107. The reasons for the above causation may not be unconnected to the fact that service industries are not productivity-driven in Nigeria. The Nigerian services industry's growth may be fragile and not sustainable in the short run. Further investments made in the sector therefore limit further growth due to the presence of corruption and institutional failure in all facets of the nation's economy. While the one-year lag values of bank credit to the service sector BCSS (-1) and financial deepening FD (-1) have positive effects on the service sector in Nigeria, trade openness (TOP) has an unstable effect in the short run and could not be sustained over a longer period. This is because the coefficient of TOP shows a positive effect (0.003193) on the service sector, while its lag values show a negative effect.

Long Run Result for Model Three

Table 14: Long-Run Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG(BCSS)	0.634535	0.170366	3.724548	0.0017
FD	-0.015058	0.006234	-2.415485	0.0273
INF	0.002452	0.000734	3.339385	0.0039
TOP	-0.206942	0.182842	-1.131808	0.2734
C	2.256644	1.431270	1.576672	0.1333

Sources; Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

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In the long run, the coefficient of bank credit to the service sector (BCSS) is a positive determinant (0.634536). This means that the service sector depends greatly on credit from commercial banks. On one hand, the coefficient of financial deepening is a negative determinant of service sector performance. A unit increase in financial deepening will, all things being equal, amount to a 0.075058 unit decrease in service sector performance in Nigeria. This exposition contradicts theoretical expectations, and it could be linked to Nigeria's frequent diversion of funds for personal consumption or the application of released funds to irrelevant services. The coefficient of inflation, on the other hand, has a positive causal effect on service sector performance. A unit increase in inflation will, all things being equal, amount to a 0.002452 unit increase in service sector performance in Nigeria. This outcome is not consistent with theoretical expectations (a priori), and it could be an increase in inflation. Higher profits, better investment returns, increased productivity, and more employment in the service sector may have resulted.

Diagnostic Checking

Table 15: Post Estimation Test Summary

S/N	Test	t-stat	Prob	OBS ^x R	Prob
1.	Residual normality Test	JB/2.846419	0.340940		
2.	Breuch Godfrey Serial Correlation	2.50855	0.1151		
3.	Heteroskedastically Test	0.832434	0.6490	16.86532	0.5324
4.	Cusum	Stable		Stable	

Sources; Author compilation from Eviews 10.05

The post-diagnostic test for model three shows that the entire estimation is "BLUE". This is because the normality test has a Jarque-Bera statistic of 2.846419 and a probability value of 0.240940 evidencing the presence of normal distribution in the residuals. Also, the serial correlation test shows the absence of serial correlation in support of the Durbin-Watson no first-order autocorrelation in the earned output. This conclusion is premised on the fact that the f-statistic value of 250855 and its probability value of 0.1151 are greater than the 0.05 threshold. Finally, the homoscedasticity assumption of the ordinary least square is maintained since the probability value of the f-statistic (0.832434) and OBSXR-square (16.86532) has probability values of 0.6490 and 0.5324 that is greater than the 0.05 limit.

4.5 Discussion of Findings

Evidence drawn from tables 4 and 5 shows that bank credit to the manufacturing sector harms the sector in the short run and has an insignificant positive effect on the manufacturing sector in the long run. Reasons for the anomaly could be that the funds borrowed for manufacturing sector expansion were either diverted to other sectors or used for personal consumption, which does not add to the stock of exported goods and services. It could also mean that the manufacturing sectors are not competing favourably in the international market due to the increase in the price of raw materials or technological advancement to the extent that they have been discouraged or their capital or profits are not strong enough to sustain productivity over time. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no statistically significant association between bank credits and manufacturing sector performance, is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Bank credit is therefore a negative determinant of manufacturing sector performance in the short run. This assertion is consistent with the views of scholars like Andbai and Eze (2018), Chude et al. (2019), Ifeoma et al. (2019), Imoughele and Ismaila (2013), but runs contrary to the positions presented by Ogar et al. (2014), Badda (2017), Mesagan et al. (2008), and Yua et al. (2020), who asserted that bank credit affects manufacturing sector performance. Evidence from tables 9 and 10 shows that bank credit to the agricultural sector has no significant impact on agricultural sector performance in the short run but was able to secure a significant impact in the long run. Based on this, we assert that the null hypothesis, which states that there is no statistically significant association between bank credit and agricultural and agricultural output, is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Bank credit is therefore a positive determinant of agricultural sector performance in Nigeria. This result is consistent with the work of Sogules and Nkoro (2016), Enyim et al. (2013), Adewole et al. (2013), Athanasius (2017), and Ogbanji et al. (2012). Tables 13 and 14 show that short-run and long-run output are relevant for the examination of the effect of bank credit on the service sector in Nigeria. It was inferred that the lag value of bank credit to the service sector promotes service sector performance in the short run and the long run. This means that bank credit to the service sector plays a significant role in the performance of the service industry in Nigeria. Hence, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no statistically significant relationship between bank credit and service sector performance, is hereby rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This study supports the findings of Sreen et al. (2017) but runs contrary to the views of Okwuchukwu and Eigbirembiu (2014), Ayunku and Eweke (2014), and Olusegun et al. (2014).

5.2 Conclusion

In the study on the effect of bank credit on real sector performance, sectoral credits have a positive influence on real sector performance through the service sector and short-run and long-run effects on the agricultural sector and manufacturing sector performance in Nigeria. This can only be possible when the inflationary pressure has a mixed effect on the manufacturing sector in the short run and a positive effect on the service sector's performance. To attain such a degree of development in real sector performance, financial deepening emitted a consistent impact on the manufacturing sector in the short run, a negative impact on real sector performance in the long run, and a positive effect on the agricultural sector. Finally, trade openness has a positive short-run effect on manufacturing sector performance but a negative short-run effect on service sector performance. This means that bank credit's most effective channel of causation for the development of the real sector is the manufacturing sector's advancement.

5.3 Recommendations for policy

The following recommendations were abstracted from the study on the effect of bank credit on real sector performance in Nigeria:

- i) To improve the performance of the real sector, commercial banks should grant more loans to service industries and the manufacturing sector.
- ii) When banks lend money to the agricultural sector, they should also offer services that help farmers learn better ways to plant and harvest their crops.
- iii) Financial institutions should improve their financial deepening services to the country in order to stimulate real sector performance in Nigeria. Emphasis should be made on granting.
- iv) Investors in agricultural and manufacturing industries require leverage since their services are essential to human survival and nation's progress.
- v) Trade openness, which is the ratio of the sum of exports and imports to the gross domestic product, should be encouraged to attract more investors into the country.

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References

- Andabai, U. & Eze, G. (2018). Bank credit and manufacturing sector growth in Nigeria (1990-2017): A causality investigation. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom*, 4(3), 326-340. <https://1library.net/document/qmoj7p7y-bank-credit-manufacturing-sector-growth-nigeria-causality-investigation.html>.
- Anyanwu, C. A. (2010). An overview of current banking sector reforms and the real sector of the Nigerian economy. *Central Bank of Nigeria CBN Economic and Financial Review*, 48(4), 31-57.
- Anyanwu, J. C. (2012). An econometric investigation of determinants of foreign direct investment in Nigeria: In Investment in the Growth Process. *Proceedings of the Nigerian Economic Society Conference*, 2011. 219-40. Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Bada, O. & Tokunbo, O. (2017). The effect of banks' credits on the development of manufacturing and agricultural sectors of Nigeria's Economy. *Journal of Advanced Studies in Economics and Public Sector Management*, 5(1), 2354-4228. <http://www.internationalpolicybrief.org/images/2017/ASEPSM/ARTICLE-8.pdf>.
- Bannocks, G. (1998). *Dictionary of economics*. Penguin Books Ltd.
- Chete, L. N. (2006). *The determinants of interest rate in Nigeria*. A monograph publication of Nigeria Institute of Social and Economic Research (NISER).
- Ebi, B. O., & Emmanuel, N. (2014). Commercial bank credits and industrial subsector's growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(9), 14-27.
- Gurley, J. G. & Shaw, E. S. (1960). *Money in a theory of finance*. The Brookings Institution, 1-2.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Dr. Edward Wasurum & Adaku Chinyere Nwachukwu

- Imoighele, L. E., & Ismaila, M. (2013). Commercial bank credit accessibility and sectorial output performance in a deregulated financial market economy: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Bank Management*, 1(2), 36-59.
- Jhingan, M. L. (1998). *The economics of development and planning*. Vrinda Publishing
- John, E. & Iorember, P. (2016). Commercial bank credit and manufacturing sector output in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 7(16), 189-202. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234647629.pdf>
- Lovemore, M., Gladness, L. Monametsi, I. P. (2017). Bank lending and manufacturing sector growth in Zimbabwe. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 6(4), 1-14. http://www.ijirset.com/upload/2017/april/3_BANK.pdf
- Muftau, A. I. (2003). Commercial bank credit to the agricultural sector and the Nigerian economy: An analysis of the future trend. *A Journal of Department of Business Administration*, 28(32), 1-13.
- National Bureau of Statistics (2016). *The Nigerian economy: Past, present and future*. The Nigerian economic outlook 2016. www.nigerianstat.gov.ng.
- National Bureau of Statistics (2016). *The Nigerian economy: Past, present and future*. The Nigerian economic outlook 2016. www.nigerianstat.gov.ng.
- Nwankwo, O. (2013). Agricultural financial in Nigeria: An empirical study of Nigerian agricultural co-operative and rural development bank (NACRDB). *Journal of Management Research*, 5(2), 28-44.
- Obansa, I. & Madeuekwe, J. (2012). The impact of agricultural financing on the Nigeria economic growth. *Research consults*. <https://researchconsults.ng/the-impact-of-agricultural-financing-on-the-nigeria-economic-growth/>.
- Ogar, A, Nkamare, S. E. & Charles, E. (2014). Commercial bank credit and its contributions on manufacturing sector in Nigeria. *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 5(22), 12-24.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Dr. Edward Wasurum & Adaku Chinyere Nwachukwu

- Ogege, S. & Boloupremo, T. (2014). Deposit money banks and economic Growth in Nigeria. *Financial Assets and Investing*, 5, 41-50
- Oleka, C. D., Ume, E. B., Obasikene, A. C., Nwadike, A. O. & Okoyeuzu, C. (2017). The relative impact of bank credit on manufacturing sector in *Nigeria. International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 7(2), 89-95.
- Oshikoya, T. W. (1992). Interest rate liberalization, savings, investment and growth: The case of Kenya savings and development. *Journal of Economics*, 16(3), 305-320.
- Schumpeter, J. A. (1911). *The theory of economic development*. M: Harvard University Press.
- Sogules, I. W. & Nkoro, E. (2016). The impact of bank credits to agricultural and manufacturing sectors on economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Research*, 2(4), 74-78.
- Tahir, S., Shehzadi, I., Ali, I. & Rizwan, U. M. (2015). Impact of bank lending on economics growth in Pakistan: An empirical study of lending to private sector. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 5, 565-576. <http://www.10.4236/ajibm.2015.58056>
- Uremadu, S. O. (2005). Determinants of banking systems credit to the Nigerian economy in a liberalised financial system: An empirical analysis, for publication in BIJAR, BUK Kano.
- Vaggi G., Groenewegen P. (2003) Knut Wicksell, 1851–1926: Interest and prices. In: *A concise history of economic thought*. Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230505803_25.